

Recent innovation in sustainable use of agricultural waste (Parali) in to biofuel

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ABSTRACT

The main energy sources at the moment are fossil fuels (coal, petroleum, and natural gas), but due to their alarming pace of use, there is concern that these will run out within the next 70 years. As a result, finding a new energy source is necessary. Among the many options, turning agricultural wastes like rice bran, wheat straw and maize cob into valuable products has received a lot of attention. Different paths for biomass conversion can be chosen depending on the qualities of the biomass (fiber analysis, proximate and final analysis, high combustion value, etc.). Less lignin is desirable for biodegradation process since it may be easily broken down at lower temperatures. Biogas (CH₄, CO₂, and H₂S) and valuable alcohols are among the end products. Timber material is favored for thermal decomposition since it is difficult to degrade. H₂, CO, CH₄, CO₂, and traces of other gases are produced during gasification. Pyrolysis produces three beneficial compounds (bio-oil, biochar, and pyrolytic gas). By removing CO₂ and H₂S from the stream using an absorbent approach, biogas can be improved. The finished goods can replace current conventional energy sources and have applications in a variety of industries.

Keywords

Fossil fuel, Biomass, Hydrocracking, Pyrolysis

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METRO TECH

1. Introduction

On average, 23.72 million tonnes of food are produced worldwide each day, and 21% of the world's greenhouse gas emissions are produced by agriculture [1]. Agricultural wastes, hardwood, softwood, and grass are among the four categories that make up lignocellulosic biomass [2]. Normally, these biomasses are disposed of without being treated, which can pollute the environment and add to the load on the environment. The two types of agricultural wastes are wastes from the areas and wastes from processing. After harvesting crops, field wastes such as stems, leaves, and stalks are left over. Waste left over from accessing crops involves seeds, peels, husks, and other materials [3]. Biofuels can be produced from the lignocellulosic biomass, which is composed of hemicellulose, cellulose, and lignin and comes from agricultural waste [4]. Agricultural waste must typically go through primary treatment procedures in order to be broken down into smaller elements for biofuel production. A well-liked thermochemical technique for producing biofuels, particularly biochar, bio-oil, and syngas, is radiation pyrolysis. The conversion of biomass resources, such as oil, synthesis gas, alcohols, and sugars, into liquid biofuels has also been investigated using a variety of pathway.

2. Primary Treatment

Waste lignocellulose can be used to produce methane, carbohydrates, enzymes, amino acids, and other materials [5]. However, the potential uses of lignocellulose waste materials are often restricted by disposal practices. As was already described, lignocellulosic biomass can be turned into biofuels, which has many benefits. Lignocellulose are Carbon di oxide neutral material which doesn't add any new carbon in environment [6].

Before turning biomass into biofuels, it must undergo processing in order to break down the biomass's complex cell wall. Typically, lignocellulosic biomass is pretreated using physical, chemical, and biological methods. Pretreatment is primarily used to hydrolyze sugars, make energy use as efficient as possible, and lower the cost of producing biofuels [7]. Physical pretreatment, which includes radiation, cutting, and milling, is reasonably affordable and practical. Previous research on wheat straw found that pretreatment at 180°C increased biofuel yield by 53% compared to unpretreated wheat straw [8].

In recent years, more environmentally friendly pretreatment techniques, such as those utilising ultrasound, electron beams, and pulsed electric fields, have been researched. These renewable technology methods' poor efficiency and restricted capacity for industrial scaling are serious drawbacks. Pretreatment simplifies the transformation of biomass into biofuel by separating it into its hemicellulose, cellulose, and lignin constituents.

The use of diluted acid is a growingly common chemical pretreatment technique. The most widely used acid is diluted sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4), which is preferred over concentrated sulfuric acid because it offers a faster reaction rate. This pretreatment method has been used to study switchgrass, corn stover, and rapeseed straw. Solubilization of these lignocellulosic biomasses has been observed with high pentose sugar yields [6]. Bioethanol is frequently produced using a pretreatment with dilute acid [7]. Ammonia-based pretreatment is a non-corrosive, low-cost alternative to chemical pretreatment. This technique works well with agricultural waste biomass that contains little lignin. Ammonia molecules split into H^+ and NH_2 , which causes chemical bonds in lignin and sugar to break.

The primary distinction between ammonia fibre explosion/expansion (AFEX) and the ammonia-based chemical pretreatment is that AFEX utilises anhydrous liquid ammonia. AFEX is a physical and chemical pretreatment. For this method, switchgrass and maize straw yield have historically been used. It works by exposing the biomass to hydrate liquid ammonia at increased pressure and between 60 and 120°C, effectively producing ethanol from the source biomass. Although AFEX is efficient at removing lignin, the use of ammonia as a chemical treatment causes environmental issues [2].

3. Microwave Pyrolysis

When comparison to thermochemical conversion, the biochemical conversion process is less effective and necessitates pretreatment procedures for the lignocellulosic elements. The resistance of plants' and animals' cell walls to hydrolytic enzymes, which is required to process biomass, is known as biomass intransigence [9]. As an alternative, agricultural waste is converted into biofuels using thermochemical conversion techniques, and the five key processes are combustion, pyrolysis, gasification, combustion, and hydrothermal liquefaction [4].

Plastic, leftover biomass and agricultural residues can all be processed using pyrolysis technology if they form a barrier that prevents heat from passing through to the interior of the material. In contrast to traditional pyrolysis, microwave pyrolysis utilizes a particular pyrolysis reactor design that is both easier to use and more effective [10]. Furthermore, compared to combustion, microwave pyrolysis uses less energy and emits fewer NO_2 and SO_2 emissions [4].

Agricultural waste containing hemicellulose, cellulose, and lignin is converted by microwave pyrolysis into charcol, vegetable-oil, and synthetic gas, all of which are useful byproducts. The internal heating that takes place during the microwave process is faster and more effective than traditional pyrolysis [11]. Plant based-oil is also used in boiler and heating system in combustion while biochar is a solid typically used for as a cooking fuel [9]. Hemicellulose generally transforms into

activated carbon and non-condensable syngas; cellulose typically transforms into syngas and bio-oil; and lignin mainly transforms into biochar.

Pyrolysis, which has high energy consumption, heats biomass using thermal heat sources like electrical energy. To combat this, microwave-assisted pyrolysis can be powered by solar photovoltaic (PV) electricity (MAP). Rural areas benefit from solar PV because it lessens their reliance on traditional energy sources [9]. Rice straw, a typical crop byproduct, was used to test the viability of solar PV as a MAP power source. Microwave power between 300 and 700 W caused an increase in bio-oil yield, but the same amount and quality with or without additives resulted in a reduction in biochar yield in both experiments.

Another investigation into solar-powered microwave pyrolysis was conducted, but this time, corncobs rather than rice husk was the subject. The idea was to make the most of the abundant biomass feedstock in India, corn stover, by turning it into wood vinegar and biochar. Usually, corn stover is burned to get rid of it, but this is hazardous to the environment and can be utilized to make more useful things like wood vinegar. Using a sedimentation process, wood vinegar is made from bio-oil. After sitting for two to three months, the crude bio-oil separates into two layers; the top layer, which is reddish-brown, is wood vinegar, and the bottom layer, which is brown, is tar. As a wood preservative, herbicide, or food flavouring agent, this wood vinegar is useful in the agricultural industry.

Due to its affordability and accessibility, 5% biochar was used in the experiment as an additive to increase the yield of bio-oil. During pyrolysis, the biochar additive was used for microwave absorption. Different microwave power values of 350, 550, 750, and 950 Watts and various reaction times of 15, 20, and 25 minutes were noted. Additionally, tested were values of 5, 10, 15, 20, and 25% for the additive ratio. It was found that a 5% additive ratio produced a 31-weight percent yield of wood vinegar as opposed to a 28-weight percent yield in the absence of additive. The experiment then used this additive ratio as a reference point, and the outcomes are shown in Figure 1.

The occurrence of the bio-char additive is generally associated with an increase in the production of bio-oil. In addition, yields of 34.1 weight % of biochar and 31.01 weight % of wood vinegar were discovered. The experiment's findings show that it is possible to successfully produce useful pyrolysis ingredients for the agricultural industry as well as biofuel by using a renewable and abundant source.

Figure 1. Experiment outcome

4. Flight Fuels

The amount of jet fuel used by commercial airlines increased from 260 million m^3 /year in 2005-6 to more than 345 million m^3 /year in 2018-19 and is predicted to rise even further [13]. The aviation industry currently emits 669 million tonnes of CO_2 annually, and by 2050, that amount is expected to rise six times [14]. Biofuels are used in the road, rail, and maritime sectors, but the commercial aircraft sector is predicted to experience the most positive changes in terms of reducing emissions of greenhouse gases and dependence on oil [15]. Nevertheless, since biomass has a high weight percentage of oxygen, producing bio-aviation fuels that meet ASTM (American Society for Testing Materials) and EU standards is challenging [13]. The requirements for jet fuels, including their density, viscosity, power density, and other characteristics, are listed in ASTM D1655-09 [14].

Because biomass contains oxygenated hydrocarbons rather than the deoxygenated hydrocarbons found in petroleum, biomass must be converted using different technologies than petroleum (Figure 2). Sugar or Sugar based products are used for the production of avian fuel by catalytic methods. Two pathways are used for the prediction of avian fuel which are depends on feed stock of oil to avian and alcohol to avian. Broadly speaking, renewable sources for bio-aviation fuel include solid, liquid, and gas-based materials. Vegetable and algal oils are examples of oil-based feedstocks, along with lignocellulosic biomass and syngas and biogas [17].

Figure 2. Sugar based products

With high pressure and temperatures between 250 and 400 °C, catalytic hydro treating is used to convert oil into aviation fuel, producing hydro processed renewable jet fuel as a by-product. Metals supported by noble metals and metals supported by alumina are employed as catalysts. During the hydrotreating process, the unsaturation in the vegetable oil feedstocks turn into branched hydrocarbons. The lack of cycloalkanes or aromatics produced by hydrotreating is a drawback of the oil-to-aviation process. Gas-to-jet involves the gasifier of biomass to produce syngas, which is then subjected to Fischer-Tropsch synthesis to produce hydrocarbons in the C1–C50 range. A carbon source is gasified at high temperatures to create a gas. However, the Fischer-Tropsch process' efficiency is constrained by the impurities in biomass and the oxygenated hydrocarbons. Because methane could form and catalysts could deteriorate, the Fischer-Tropsch process's high heat must be removed. Due to additional steps needed to mitigate these issues, the gas-to-jet route is difficult for the production of jet fuel. Furthermore, aromatics are not created by this process.

Through the alcohol-to-jet process, oxygenated fuel can be changed into hydrocarbons that work with the current generation of transportation fuels. Last but not least, whereas jet fuels require longer carbon chains and sugars and their derivatives only contain six carbon atoms, the sugar transformation pathway of sugars to hydrocarbons is complicated. The next step is to remove oxygen from the products using procedures like hydrogenation and dehydration [14].

2.5% w/v zinc NPs were used as catalysts in a experiment that used cooking oil from Egyptian fast food restaurants to make jet fuel because they can decrease the H/C ratio in heat cracking [17]. The waste cooking oil had 10.61 weight% oxygen and was made up of 39.8% C8–C16 and 60.1% C17–C19. Thermal cracking at 400–450°C was found to be the most efficient method for breaking long carbon chains into smaller chains of C8–C16. 96% of the crude bio fuel was obtained after the initial thermal cracking process, and after distillation, 51% of the bio fuels for other uses and 49% of the bio aviation fuel were obtained. The results of the experiment showed that the waste cooking oils could be hydro cracked to produce bio-jet fuel with low oxygen content and no corrosive substances.

5. Conclusion

The lignocellulose biomass feedstock is broken down into smaller components during the pretreatment processes required for biochemical conversion methods, which facilitates the conversion of the input biomass into biofuels. There have been discussions of diluted acid, acid, ammonia-based, and ammonia fibre explosion/expansion pretreatment techniques, each with pros and cons. Biomass recalcitrance results in inefficiency, which can be overcome by thermochemical conversion techniques like microwave pyrolysis. Large weight percentages of biofuel were produced in solar energy experiments using rice straw and corn stover as energy sources. The four main routes for converting aviation fuel are also described because they have a great chance of drastically reducing greenhouse gas emissions.

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